

Synthesis of 5-Hydroxy-1,2-Diphenylindole Derivatives

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1-*p*-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenylindole was synthesised by the Nenitzescu method and converted to various *N*-substituted 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenyltryptamines. Attempts to debenzylate the above tryptamines by hydrogenation with Pd/C gave the corresponding 5-hydroxy-1,2-diphenyl-*N*-substituted tryptamines resulting from debromination during the process. Similar debromination with ethyl 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylate and its 4-dimethylamino derivative is reported.

In continuation of our previous work on the synthesis of indole derivatives of biological interest,¹⁻⁴ we report here the synthesis of some 5-hydroxy-1,2-diphenyl indole derivatives. Ethyl β -*p*-bromoanilino-cinnamate (1) was reacted with *p*-benzoquinone to get ethyl 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylate (2) which was benzyloxy to yield 5-benzyloxyindolecarboxylate (3). This was converted to the acid (4) which decarboxylated to yield 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenylindole (5). The indole (5) was reacted⁵ with oxalyl chloride to get 3-indolyglyoxyl chloride which on subsequent treatment with pyrrolidine and cyclohexylamine gave the corresponding amides (6 & 7). Reduction of these amides (6 & 7) with LAH provided the required 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-

benzyloxy-2-phenyltryptamines (8 & 9) which were hydrogenated over Pd/C (10%) with a view to obtain the free 5-hydroxy analogues. During debenzylation, debromination also occurred to yield 5-hydroxy-1,

(8 - 11)

R ₁	R ₂	X
(8) Pyrrolidino	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	Br
(9) Cyclohexylamino	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	Br
(10) Pyrrolidino	-H	-H
(11) Cyclohexylamino	-H	-H

R ₁	R ₂
(2) -COOC ₂ H ₅	-H
(3) -COOC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅
(4) -COOH	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅
(5) -H	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅
(6) Pyrrolidinoglyoxyl	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅
(7) Cyclohexylamidoglyoxyl	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅

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2-diphenyltryptamines (10 & 11). The C-Br stretching band (around 520 s cm^{-1}) observed in the IR spectra of bromo compounds (8 & 9) is not present in the spectra of debrominated products (10 & 11).

Similarly, when the 4-isogramine (12) was treated with Raney Ni in refluxing ethanol, the elimination of bromine took place and ethyl 4-methyl-5-hydroxy-1, 2-diphenylindole-3-carboxylate (13) was obtained. The IR spectrum of (12) shows C-Br stretching band at 515 s cm^{-1} , which is absent in the I. R. spectrum of (13). The PMR results of (12) and (13) agree with their structures. Aromatic region ($6.6-7.66\ \delta$) of (12) accounts for eleven protons while that of (13) ($6.76-7.66\ \delta$) for twelve protons. The C-6 proton signal of (12) is observed as doublet ($J=9\ \text{Hz}$) at 6.71 and the J value indicates *ortho*-coupling. This confirms the presence of dimethylaminomethyl group [$4.13\ \delta$ ($-\text{CH}_2$); $2.45\ \delta$ two methyls] at C-4. Further, compound (13) has been synthesised by an unambiguous method from 4-isogramine (16) via (15).

The elimination of halogen bound to aromatic compounds has been reported⁶ during hydrogenation using Pd/C (10%) or Raney Ni and the alkaline medium has been noted^{6a} to accelerate the elimination process. During the debenzoylation of 5-benzyloxytryptamines (8 & 9) and the conversion of 4-isogramine (12) to 4-methylindole derivative (13), the reaction medium is basic due to the basic nitrogen present in the starting compounds (8, 9 & 12). Further, when ethyl 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylate (2), which does not contain any basic nitrogen was hydrogenated over Pd/C (10%) or Raney Ni or refluxed with Raney Ni in ethanol the bromine was eliminated yielding ethyl 5-hydroxy-1, 2, diphenylindole-3-carboxylate (15) whose structure was confirmed by an unambiguous synthesis from ethyl β -anilinoacrylate (14) and *p*-benzoquinone. The above results appear to indicate the labile nature of the bromine situated at the *para* position of the phenyl group attached to indole nitrogen.

Experimental

Ethyl β -*p*-bromoanilinoacrylate (1)

A mixture of ethyl benzoylacetate (35 g), *p*-bromoaniline (35 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 drops) was heated at $65-70^\circ$ for 16 hr. It was cooled and the product was recrystallised from alcohol as yellow flakes (30 g), m. p. 114° .

(Found : C, 58.72; H, 4.84; N, 4.21. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_2$ Br requires C, 58.95; H, 4.62; N, 4.05%.)

Ethyl 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylate (2)

A solution of cinnamate (1) (34 g) and *p*-benzoquinone (21 g) in ethanol was refluxed for 16 hr and

the residue obtained on removing ethanol under suction was purified by crystallisation from benzene. The product on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate gave colourless tiny needles (8 g), m. p. 250° .

(Found : C, 63.13; H, 4.07; N, 3.36. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ Br requires C, 63.30; H, 4.23; N, 3.21%; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{OH}}$ 3290 cm^{-1} (OH); 1648 s (C=O) and 505 s C-Br).

Ethyl 1-*p*-bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylate (3)

Benzyl chloride (1.8 ml) was added to a solution of hydroxyindole (2) (6 g) and sodium hydroxide (1.8 g) in a mixture of water (12 ml) and alcohol (36 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux on a water bath until crystalline benzyloxyindole (3) separated (10-15 min). The benzyloxyindole was collected and was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) as colourless plates (2 g), m. p. 203° .

(Found : C, 68.71; H, 4.69; N, 2.78. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{NO}_3$ Br requires C, 68.60; H, 4.56; N, 2.66%.)

1-*p*-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylic acid (4)

The carboxylate (3) (1.9 g) in benzene (20 ml) was hydrolysed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (25%, 30 ml) by heating under reflux for 5 hr. The potassium salt of the acid (4) obtained on evaporating the solvents was suspended in ice water (100 ml) and acidified with acetic acid. The precipitate was collected and recrystallised from aqueous dioxan as colourless granules (1.5 g), m. p. 254° .

(Found : C, 67.40; H, 4.30; N, 2.96. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_3$ Br requires C, 67.47; H, 4.02; N, 2.81%.)

1-*p*-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenylindole (5)

The acid (4) (3 g) was heated at $255-258^\circ$ for 20 min. (i.e. until the evolution of CO_2 ceased) and the residue was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) to get the benzyloxyindole (5) as colourless needles (1.8 g), m. p. 157° .

(Found : C, 71.54; H, 4.57; N, 3.17. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}$ Br requires C, 71.36; H, 4.40; N, 3.08%.)

1-*p*-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-3-(2-*N*-pyrrolidinyloxy) indole (6)

The benzyloxyindole (5) (2 g) in dry ether (300 ml) was treated with oxalyl chloride (2.8 ml) according to the procedure described earlier⁵ and the greenish yellow tiny needles of 3-indolylglyoxyyl chloride was collected (1.9 g), m. p. $138-139^\circ$; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{C=O}}$ 1640 s (conjugated C=O); 1795 s (COCl). This indolylglyoxyyl chloride (1.8) was treated with pyrrolidine

(4 ml) and the separated amide (6) was recrystallised from aqueous dioxan as colourless needles (1.7 g), m.p. 194°.

(Found : C, 68.18 ; H, 4.75 ; N, 4.96. $C_{28}H_{27}N_2O_3Br$ requires C, 68.39 ; H, 4.66 ; N, 4.84%) $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ 1628s (C=O) ; absent (OH).

1-p-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-3-(2-N-cyclohexylamidoglyoxyl) indole (7)

Following the procedure described for (6), the amide (7) was prepared from indole (5) (2 g), oxalyl chloride (2.8 ml) and cyclohexyl amine (4 ml). It was recrystallised from aqueous dioxan as colourless tiny needles (1.8 g), m.p. 216°.

(Found : C, 69.04 ; H, 5.21 ; N, 4.78. $C_{38}H_{31}N_2O_3Br$ requires C, 69.18 ; H, 5.11 ; N, 4.61%.)

1-p-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-3-(2-N-pyrrolidinoethyl) indole (8)

A solution of the amide (6) (1.6 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (100 ml) was added to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (2.5 g) in dry ether (100 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 24 hr. It was cooled, the complex was decomposed with sodium hydroxide solution (15%, 2.5 ml) and water (5 ml). The white precipitate was filtered off and the residue obtained on evaporating solvents was crystallised from alcohol as colourless plates (1 g), m.p. 128°.

(Found : C, 71.93 ; H, 5.46 ; N, 5.21 ; $C_{33}H_{31}N_2O_3Br$ requires C, 71.86 ; H, 5.33 ; N, 5.08%) $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ absent (OH & C=O) ; 1618w and 1595m (Ar C=C) ; 520s (C-Br).

1-p-Bromophenyl-5-benzyloxy 2-phenyl-3-(2-N-cyclohexylaminoethyl) indole (9)

The tryptamine (9) was prepared from amide (7) (2 g) and lithium aluminium hydride (3 g) according to the procedure given for (8) and the product was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (60-80°) as colourless plates (1.2 g), m.p. 170°.

(Found : C, 72.63 ; H, 5.91 ; N, 4.88. $C_{38}H_{35}N_2O_3Br$ requires C, 72.52 ; H, 6.05 ; N, 4.84%) $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ absent (C=O) ; 3290s (NH) and 520s (C-Br).

1, 2-Diphenyl-5-hydroxy-3-(2-N-pyrrolidinoethyl) indole (10)

A mixture of benzyloxytryptamine (8) (0.5 g) and palladium charcoal (10%, 0.45 g) in methanol was hydrogenated in a Parr low pressure apparatus at 53-5 lb/sq. inch. for 10-12 hr. The catalyst was filtered off and the residue obtained from the filtrate on removing methanol under suction, was recrystallised from methanol as pale yellow microscopic needles (0.2 g), m.p. 205°.

(Found : C, 81.46 ; H, 6.93 ; N, 7.41. $C_{26}H_{26}N_2O$ requires C, 81.68 ; H, 6.81 ; N, 7.35%) $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ 3430br (OH) ; 1608 and 1560w (Ar C=C) ; absent (C-Br).

1, 2-Diphenyl-5-hydroxy-3-(2-N-cyclohexylaminoethyl) indole (11)

Following the procedure described for (10), the benzyloxytryptamine (9) (0. g) was hydrogenated over Pd/C (10% 0.45 g) and the product was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as pale yellow granules (0.2 g), m.p. 218°(d).

(Found : C, 82.01 ; H, 7.13 ; N, 6.65. $C_{28}H_{30}N_2O$ requires C, 81.94 ; H, 7.22 ; N, 6.83%) $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ 3340br (NH/OH) ; 1605s and 1560m (Ar C=C) ; absent (C-Br).

Ethyl 1-p-bromophenyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylate (12)

The hydroxyindole (2) (4 g) in dioxan (20 ml) was subjected to the Mannich reaction with dimethylamine (30%, 3 ml), formaldehyde (37%, 1 ml) and acetic acid (8 ml) according to the procedure described earlier⁴ and the 4-isogramine (12) obtained was crystallised from aqueous alcohol as colourless plates (3 g), m.p. 183°.

(Found : C, 63.6 ; H, 4.91 ; N, 5.54. $C_{26}H_{25}N_2O_3Br$ requires C, 63.30 ; H, 5.07 ; N, 5.68%) $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ 515s (C-Br) ; PMR, $CDCl_3$ (TMS), δ ppm 0.88 (3H, t, J=7Hz ester CH_3) ; 4.03 (2H, q, ester $-CH_2-$), 2.45 (6H, s, $N(CH_3)_2$) ; 4.13 (2H, s, $N-CH_2$) ; 6.71 (1H, d, J=9Hz, C-6H) ; 10.88 (1H, br, C-5 OH) ; 6.6-7.66 (11H, m, ArH).

Ethyl 4-methyl-5-hydroxy-1, 2-diphenylindole-3-carboxylate (13)

Method A

A mixture of 4-isogramine (12) (3 g) and Raney nickel (30 g) in ethanol (300 ml) was heated under reflux for 24 hr and then filtered. The residue obtained on evaporating ethanol under suction was crystallised from ethanol to get the pure carboxylate (13) as colourless plates (2 g), m.p. 167°.

(Found : C, 77.79 ; H, 4.35 ; N, 3.85. $C_{24}H_{21}NO_3$ requires C, 77.62 ; H, 4.49 ; N, 3.77%) ; TLC [Silica gel G, benzene-ethyl acetate (6 : 1)] Rf 0.62 ; $\nu_{max}^{Nujol} cm^{-1}$ 3405s (OH) ; 1653 (C=O) and absent (C-Br) ; PMR, DMSO- d_6 (TMS) δ ppm 0.95 (3H, t J=7Hz, ester CH_3) ; 4.1 (2H, q, ester $-CH_2-$) ; 3.46 (3H, s, C-4 CH_3) ; 8.96 (1H, s, C-5 OH) ; 6.76-7.66 (12H, m, ArH).

Method B

Following the procedure described in method A, a mixture of 4-isogramine (16) (0.3 g) and Raney nickel (3 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed and the product was crystallised from alcohol as colourless

plates (0.25 g), m.p. 167°. This showed no depression in mixed m.p. with (13) and exhibited identical TLC behaviour with (13).

Ethyl β -anilino-cinnamate (14)

Ethyl benzoylacetate (30 g) was reacted with aniline (20 g) according to the procedure given for (1) and the product was crystallised from alcohol to get (14) as pale yellow plates (25 g), m.p. 65°.

(Found : C, 76.29 ; H, 6.48 ; N, 5.36. $C_{17}H_{17}NO_2$ requires C, 76.40 ; H 6.37 ; N, 5.24%).

Ethyl 5-hydroxy-1, 2-diphenylindole-3-carboxylate (15)

Method A

A solution of the cinnamate (14) (10 g) and benzoquinone (7 g) in alcohol (100 ml) and acetic acid (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 16 hr and the residue obtained on removing solvent under suction was purified from benzene and then repeatedly crystallised from ethyl acetate to get pure carboxylate (15) as colourless plates (2 g), m.p. 264° ; TLC [Silica gel G, benzene-ethyl acetate (7 : 1)] Rf 0.54.

(Found : C, 77.46 ; H, 5.21 ; N, 4.03. $C_{23}H_{19}NO_3$ requires C, 77.31 ; H, 5.32 ; N, 3.92%).

Method B : Hydrogenation of bromo compound (2) with Pd/C catalyst

A mixture of bromo compound (2) (0.2 g) and Pd/C (10%, 0.2 g) in methanol (100 ml) was hydrogenated according to the procedure described for (10) and the product was recrystallised from ethyl acetate to get (15) as colourless plates (0.1 g), m.p. 264°. No depression in mixed m.p. with sample (15) synthesised according to method A and showed identical TLC behaviour.

Method C : Hydrogenation of bromo compound (2) with Raney Nickel catalyst

The bromocompound (2) (0.3 g) in methanol (150ml) was hydrogenated over Raney Ni as described in Method B and the product on crystallisation from ethyl acetate was obtained as colourless plates (0.12 g), m.p. 264°. No depression in mixed m.p. with synthetic sample (15) (Cf. Method A) and showed identical TLC behaviour.

Method D

The bromocompound (2) (0.2 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was treated with Raney nickel (6 g) as described for (13) (Method A) and the product was crystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless plates (0.16 g), m.p. 264°. No depression in mixed m.p. with synthetic sample (15) and showed identical TLC behaviour.

Ethyl 4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-1, 2-diphenylindole-3-carboxylate (16)

Following the procedure described for (12), the 4-isogramine (16) was prepared from the corresponding hydroxyindole (15) (0.6 g), dimethylamine (0.6 ml) and formaldehyde (0.2 ml) and crystallised from aqueous methanol as colourless tiny needles (0.45 g), m.p. 184°.

(Found : C, 75.48 ; H, 6.12 ; N, 6.87. $C_{26}H_{26}N_2O_3$ requires C, 75.37 ; H, 6.28 ; N, 6.76%).

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